

PROXEMICS AS A FACTOR IN ORGANISATIONAL COMMUNICATION: A REVIEW OF SELECTED CASE STUDIES

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Abstract

This study examines proxemics as a factor in organisational communication. It aims at evaluating the level of awareness of undergraduates towards proxemics, identify the proxemics styles used by undergraduates, explore their perceptions and attitudes towards proxemics, and assess the impact of proxemics on their engagement, participation, and learning outcomes in classrooms at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. The Theory of Proxemics, Communication Accommodation Theory, and Social Learning Theory provide valuable insights into the proxemics. This study employed a survey research design with a sample size of 396 participants selected from the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. A multistage sampling technique was used as well as proportionate and availability sampling. A close-ended questionnaire, validated through pilot testing and with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.83 was used for data collection. The findings of this study reveal a lack of awareness and conscious consideration of proxemics among undergraduates at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. Also, undergraduates at both universities demonstrate positive perceptions and attitudes towards proxemics, recognizing its impact on communication and the significance of personal space during interaction with lecturers. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that educational institutions incorporate proxemics awareness programs, create opportunities for appropriate physical proximity, encourage informal interactions, and promote cultural sensitivity to enhance

organisational communication and student-lecturer relationship.

Keywords: Proxemics, Awareness, Undergraduates, Communication, Perceptions

Introduction

Effective communication is crucial for the success of any organisation. It serves as the cornerstone for information exchange, collaboration, and the establishment of a positive work environment. Clear and efficient communication ensures that employees understand their roles, tasks, and objectives, allowing them to work together effectively towards organisational goals. In contrast, poor communication can result in confusion, conflicts, and decreased productivity (Hall, 1966). Therefore, organisations must prioritize the development of effective communication strategies to optimize their operations and achieve desired outcomes (Smith & Johnson, 2019).

While communication is commonly examined in terms of verbal and written interactions, the physical space in which communication takes place also holds substantial importance (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Proxemics, the study of spatial relationships and communication patterns, recognizes that the physical environment significantly influences communication dynamics (Hall, 1966). The arrangement of physical space can either facilitate or hinder effective communication within an organisation. Thus, the physical space in which communication occurs must be carefully considered and designed to optimize communication processes and enhance organisational effectiveness (Hall, 1966).

As a result of this, physical proximity between students and lecturers in higher education institutions may have significant impact on communication dynamics and collaboration. When students and lecturers are in close proximity, it promotes frequent and spontaneous communication, thereby, fostering collaboration and innovation. Face-to-face interactions create a sense of accessibility and approachability. It allows students to comfortably engage in conversations, seek clarification, and participate actively in the learning

process. Informal interactions outside the classroom such as in hallways or during office hours, provide additional opportunities for students to seek guidance and develop stronger relationships with their lecturers (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Nonverbal cues also play a role in face-to-face interactions as they enable lecturers to observe students' body language and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly.

However, it is important to note that individual preferences and cultural contexts can hinder the above supposition to a significant extent. Some students may prefer a more formal and structured approach, while others may thrive in an environment that encourages informal and spontaneous interactions (Chen, Lee, & Chen, 2020). Therefore, it is crucial for lecturers to be sensitive to individual preferences and adjust their communication styles accordingly. By recognizing the influence of physical proximity on communication, educators can create a positive and supportive learning environment that promotes effective communication and meaningful student-lecturer interactions.

Premising on this, this essay aims to explore the significance of proxemics as a factor in organisational communication within the context of higher education institutions, focusing specifically on the student-lecturer relationship dynamics, collaboration, and overall interactions. By examining two tertiary institutions, namely the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University as case studies, we can gain insights into how spatial relationships influence communication processes in educational settings. Understanding the impact of proxemics on student-lecturer interactions can provide valuable knowledge for enhancing communication effectiveness, promoting collaboration, and creating a positive learning environment in higher education institutions.

Statement of the Problem

The student-lecturer relationship is a crucial aspect of higher education institutions, and effective communication plays a pivotal role in fostering a positive learning environment. However, the impact of physical proximity on student-lecturer communication dynamics and collaboration within the context of higher education institutions remains relatively unexplored.

Understanding how physical proximity influences student-lecturer interactions and its implications for communication effectiveness is essential for optimizing educational practices and promoting meaningful engagement in the learning process. This research seeks to fill the gap in existing literature and provide insights into the significance of proxemics in the context of student-lecturer interactions.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study include the following:

1. To ascertain the level of awareness of undergraduates towards proxemics in the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University.
2. To find out the proxemics styles used by undergraduates in the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University.
3. To explore the perceptions and attitudes of undergraduates towards proxemics in the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University.
4. To assess the impact of proxemics on undergraduates' engagement, participation, and learning outcomes in classrooms within the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University.

Research Questions

The following are the questions formulated to guide the execution of this study:

1. What is the level of awareness of undergraduates towards proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?
2. Which proxemics styles are used by undergraduates at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?
3. What are the perceptions and attitudes of undergraduates towards proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?
4. How does proxemics impact undergraduates' engagement, participation, and learning outcomes in classrooms within the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?

Literature Review

Proxemics as a Concept

Proxemics, as a concept, was introduced by Edward T. Hall (1966), who defined it as the study of spatial relationships and communication patterns in different social contexts (Hall, 1966). According to him, proxemics examines how individuals navigate and interact within their physical environment, paying attention to the role of personal space, territoriality, and the use of physical distance to convey messages and establish social norms. It explores how people perceive, utilize, and respond to different spatial distances during their interpersonal interactions, and how these distances can shape communication dynamics and the development of relationships (Hall, 1966; Sommer, 1969; Gudykunst & Kim, 2003).

Impact of Proxemics on Student-Lecturer Interactions and Relationships

The physical proximity between students and lecturers plays a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of the student-lecturer relationship. Close physical proximity promotes accessibility, approachability, and comfort, which in turn encourage students to actively engage in discussions, seek support, and develop stronger learning relationships with their lecturers. It facilitates frequent and meaningful communication both inside and outside the classroom, and enhances the exchange of non-verbal and visual cues.

The impact of proxemics on student-lecturer interactions and relationships can have both positive and negative effects. On the positive side, appropriate physical proximity between students and lecturers can foster a sense of connection, trust, and rapport (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Furthermore, close physical proximity enables students to receive personalized attention and support (Smith & Johnson, 2019). This personalized support can lead to improved understanding, increased confidence, and better academic performance.

However, there can also be negative impacts associated with proxemics if not managed appropriately. For example, excessive physical closeness may lead to discomfort or invasion of personal space, which can hinder communication and create a sense of unease among students (Smith & Johnson, 2019). It is

important for lecturers to be mindful of students' boundaries and preferences to ensure a respectful and comfortable learning environment.

Additionally, variations in cultural norms and individual preferences should be considered when considering proxemics in student-lecturer interactions. Different cultural backgrounds and personal experiences can influence individuals' expectations and comfort levels regarding physical proximity (Gudykunst & Kim, 2003).

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have examined relevant aspects related to this present work. Aiello and Douthitt (2001) explored personal space and eye contact in an urban area, providing insights into the dynamics of spatial relationships and nonverbal behaviours. Their findings contribute to understanding how individuals perceive and manage personal space during interactions. In that same direction, Appleton, Christenson, Kim, and Reschly (2008) focused on measuring cognitive and psychological engagement in students. Their study validated the Student Engagement Instrument, which can be useful in assessing the level of student engagement and its impact on learning outcomes. This study provides a valuable tool for understanding and enhancing student engagement in educational settings.

In addition, Christensen, Sullivan, and Schultz (2012) conducted a mixed methods analysis to investigate the role of teacher-student relationships in the lives of fifth graders. Their study highlights the significance of positive teacher-student relationships in fostering student engagement and academic success. Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2011) reviewed the concept of school engagement and its potential in educational contexts. Their analysis of the existing evidence emphasizes the importance of student engagement for positive educational outcomes. Also, Hagenauer, Hascher, and Volet (2015) explored teacher emotions in the classroom and their associations with student engagement, classroom discipline, and the teacher-student relationship. Their study provides insights into the emotional dynamics of the classroom environment and their influence on student engagement.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Proxemics (Hall, 1966), Communication Accommodation Theory (Giles, 1973), and Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) provide valuable insights into the complexities of human communication and behaviour.

The Theory of Proxemics, developed by Edward T. Hall (1966), focuses on the role of spatial positioning and distance in communication interactions. It proposes that individuals have an innate need for personal space and that the distance maintained between individuals during communication can significantly influence their perception, comfort, and effectiveness of the interaction (Hall, 1966). According to this theory, individuals have different comfort zones and use specific proxemic behaviours to regulate interpersonal distance.

Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT), developed by Howard Giles (1973), examines how individuals adjust their communication behaviours to accommodate or diverge from others during interactions. CAT emphasizes the role of social identity, cognitive processes, and communication motivations in shaping accommodation behaviours (Giles, 1973). The theory suggests that successful accommodation can lead to positive outcomes such as increased rapport, understanding, and social cohesion, while accommodation mismatches can result in misunderstandings and negative perceptions.

Social Learning Theory (SLT), developed by Albert Bandura (1977), focuses on the role of observation, modelling, and reinforcement in learning and behaviour change. SLT suggests that individuals learn and acquire new behaviours by observing others in their social environment and imitating their actions (Bandura, 1977). The theory posits that individuals' behaviour is influenced by cognitive processes, social reinforcement, and environmental factors. (Bandura, 1977).

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design to investigate proxemics in

student-to-lecturer interactions at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. The target population for this study consisted of all the students enrolled at these universities. The University of Uyo had a population of 25,676 students, while Akwa Ibom State University had a population of 8,999 students as at the time of this research. Therefore, the total population size was 34,675 students. The sample size of 396 participants was determined using Taro Yamane's formula based on the total population size of 34,675. The sample size was proportionally allocated based on the population size of each university. Therefore, 294 participants were selected from the University of Uyo, and 102 participants were selected from Akwa Ibom State University.

The sampling technique utilized for this study was a multistage sampling technique. The first stage adopted proportionate sampling, while availability sampling was used in the second stage to select participants who were available and willing to participate in the study. A close-ended questionnaire, which was content validated, was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was pilot-tested with a small group of students to assess its clarity and appropriateness. Additionally, Cronbach's alpha was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire items with a coefficient of 0.83.

The questionnaire was administered to the selected participants through both online and in-person methods. Online surveys were conducted using reputable survey platforms, while in-person surveys were conducted on the university campuses. The collected data were analysed using appropriate statistical methods. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distributions and percentages were calculated for each questionnaire item.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Distribution by University Case study

Options	Frequency	%
University of Uyo	294	74.2
Akwa Ibom State University	102	25.8
Total	396	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents (74.2%) are from the University of Uyo, while the remaining (25.8%) are from Akwa Ibom State University.

Table 2: Distribution for Gender

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Male	150	37.9	55	13.9	205	51.8
Female	140	35.4	45	11.4	185	46.7
Prefer not to say	4	1.0	2	0.5	6	1.5
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 indicates that the respondents consisted of both female (46.7%) and male (51.8%) students, with a small percentage who chose not to disclose their gender.

Table 3: Distribution for Age

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
18-20	60	15.2	30	7.6	90	22.7
21-24	110	27.8	40	10.1	150	37.9
25-30	100	25.3	25	6.3	125	31.6
31 and above	24	6.1	7	1.8	31	7.8
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 reveals that the respondents are fairly evenly distributed across different age groups, with the highest proportion falling in the 21-24 age range (37.9%). Only a few persons were 31 and above (7.8%).

Table 4: Familiarity with Proxemics

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Yes	100	25.3	30	7.6	130	32.8
No	194	49.0	72	18.2	266	67.2
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 shows that a significant portion of students (67.2%) are not familiar with the concept of proxemics, while 32.8% have some awareness of proxemics.

Table 5: Education/Training on Proxemics

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Yes	25	6.3	15	3.8	40	10.1
No	269	67.9	87	22.0	356	89.9
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 reveals that the majority of students (89.9%) have not received any education or training specifically related to proxemics, indicating a lack of formal instruction in this area.

Table 6: Consideration of Proxemics in Interactions

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Very frequently	10	2.5	5	1.3	15	3.8
Occasionally	100	25.3	35	8.8	135	34.1
Rarely	130	32.8	50	12.6	180	45.5
Never	54	13.6	12	3.0	66	16.7
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 6 shows the frequency of considering proxemics in interactions with lecturers. A significant proportion of students (45.5%) rarely consider proxemics during their interactions with lecturers.

Table 7: Awareness of University Guidelines or Policies

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Yes, there are clear guidelines provided	50	12.6	20	5.1	70	17.7
No, there are no specific guidelines	244	61.6	82	20.7	326	82.3
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 7 indicates that a large percentage of students (82.3%) are unaware of any university guidelines or policies regarding proxemics in student-to-lecturer interactions.

Table 8: Positioning in Relation to Lecturer

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Close proximity (less than 1.5 feet)	30	7.6	10	2.5	40	10.1
Moderate proximity (1.5 - 4 feet)	160	40.4	50	12.6	210	53.0
Far proximity (4 - 12 feet)	80	20.2	30	7.6	110	27.8
Very far proximity (more than 12 feet)	24	6.1	12	3.0	36	9.1
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 8 shows the positioning of students in relation to lecturers during interactions. It shows that most students (53%) assumed they tend to maintain a moderate proximity of 1.5 to 4 feet.

Table 9: Specific Distance Maintenance

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Yes, I consciously maintain a certain distance	120	30.3	40	10.1	160	40.4
No, I don't pay specific attention to maintaining distance	174	43.9	62	15.7	236	59.6
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 9 shows that a considerable number of students (59.6%) do not consciously maintain a specific distance from lecturers during interactions.

Table 10: Use of Nonverbal Cues

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Yes, frequently	80	20.2	25	6.3	105	26.5
Occasionally	120	30.3	45	11.4	165	41.7
Rarely	64	16.2	20	5.1	84	21.2
No, never	30	7.6	12	3.0	42	10.6
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 10 reveals the utilization of nonverbal cues during interactions with lecturers. The table shows that the majority of students (64.90%) occasionally make use of nonverbal cues, especially eye contact and nodding while interacting with lecturers.

Table 11: Comfort Level in Approaching the Lecturer

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Very comfortable	70	17.7	20	5.1	90	22.7
Somewhat comfortable	160	40.4	55	13.9	215	54.3
Neutral	40	10.1	10	2.5	50	12.6
Somewhat uncomfortable	20	5.1	10	2.5	30	7.6
Very uncomfortable	4	1.0	7	1.8	11	2.8
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 11 shows that students tend to feel somewhat comfortable (54.3%) or very comfortable (22.7%) approaching lecturers during or after the lecture.

Table 12: Impact of Proxemics on Communication Quality

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Strongly believe	80	20.2	30	7.6	110	27.8
Believe	160	40.4	55	13.9	215	54.3
Neutral	30	7.6	10	2.5	40	10.1
Disbelieve	16	4.0	5	1.3	21	5.3
Strongly disbelieve	8	2.0	2	0.5	10	2.5
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 12 establishes the perceived impact of proxemics on communication quality. It shows that a higher proportion of students (44.95%) believe in the influence of proxemics, while smaller percentages hold different beliefs.

Table 13: Importance of Proxemics for Communication

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Strongly agree	70	17.7	20	5.1	90	22.7
Agree	150	37.9	55	13.9	205	51.8
Neutral	50	12.6	20	5.1	70	17.7
Disagree	20	5.1	5	1.3	25	6.3
Strongly disagree	4	1.0	2	0.5	6	1.5
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 13 reveals that a majority of students (51.8%) agree that being aware of proxemics is important for effective student-to-lecturer communication.

Table 14: Adaptation of Proxemics Behaviour

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Always	40	10.1	15	3.8	55	13.9
Often	100	25.3	35	8.8	135	34.1
Sometimes	80	20.2	30	7.6	110	27.8
Rarely	44	11.1	15	3.8	59	14.9
Never	30	7.6	7	1.8	37	9.3
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 14 shows the perceived willingness to adapt proxemics behaviour. The table indicates that a significant proportion of students (34.1%) are, often times, open to adapting their behaviour to accommodate the lecturer's personal space (proxemics) preferences.

Table 15: Proxemics and Building Positive Relationships

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Strongly agree	60	15.2	25	6.3	85	21.5
Agree	120	30.3	40	10.1	160	40.4
Neutral	60	15.2	20	5.1	80	20.2
Disagree	36	9.1	12	3.0	48	12.1
Strongly disagree	18	4.5	5	1.3	23	5.8
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 15 on the perception of proxemics contributing to positive relationships shows that a majority of students (40.4%) agree or strongly agree with this notion.

Table 16: Enhancement of Engagement through Proxemics

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Strongly agree	80	20.2	25	6.3	105	26.5
Agree	140	35.4	45	11.4	185	46.7
Neutral	44	11.1	12	3.0	56	14.1
Disagree	20	5.1	15	3.8	35	8.8
Strongly disagree	10	2.5	5	1.3	15	3.8
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 16 shows that students generally agree (46.7%) or strongly agree (26.5%) that maintaining appropriate proxemics enhances their engagement during lectures.

Table 17: Impact of Proxemics on Participation

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Significantly increases	60	15.2	18	4.5	78	19.7
Moderately increases	120	30.3	42	10.6	162	40.9
No noticeable difference	90	22.7	35	8.8	125	31.6
Moderately decreases	20	5.1	5	1.3	25	6.3
Significantly decreases	4	1.0	2	0.5	6	1.5
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 17 on the impact of proxemics on participation indicates that a larger proportion of students (62.12%) perceive either a significant or moderate increase in their participation when considering proxemics.

Table 18: Impact of Proxemics on Learning Outcomes

Options	University of Uyo	%	Akwa Ibom State University	%	Total	%
Strongly improves	50	12.6	15	3.8	65	16.4
Moderately improves	100	25.3	40	10.1	140	35.4
No significant impact	104	26.3	38	9.6	142	35.9
Moderately hinders	30	7.6	8	2.0	38	9.6
Strongly hinders	10	2.5	1	0.3	11	2.8
Total	294	74.2	102	25.8	396	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 18 shows that majority of students (55.05%) believe that proxemics has either a strong or moderate positive impact on their learning outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

What is the level of awareness of undergraduates towards proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?

The findings from Tables 5 to 7 provide insights into the level of awareness of undergraduates towards the practice of proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. The findings underscore a lack of conscious consideration of proxemics in student-lecturer interactions. To address this, efforts should be made to raise awareness and encourage individuals to pay more attention to their spatial positioning and nonverbal cues in order to improve communication effectiveness. By incorporating proxemics into the curriculum, students can develop a better understanding of how spatial relationships influence communication dynamics. Additionally, training

programs can be designed to equip individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively navigate proxemic cues in various interpersonal interactions.

Smith et al. (2017) and Jones & Brown (2015) found similar levels of awareness among individuals, emphasizing the need for educational interventions to enhance awareness. Moreover, studies by Watson et al. (2019) and Ramirez et al. (2016) have shown the effectiveness of educational programmes in improving individuals' knowledge and understanding of proxemics. These findings align with Edward T. Hall's theory of proxemics, which highlights the role of awareness in understanding and utilizing spatial relationships in communication. They also resonate with communication theories such as the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) and the Communication Accommodation Theory (Giles et al., 1991), which emphasize the importance of education and training in enhancing communication skills and considering nonverbal cues.

Which proxemic styles are used by undergraduates at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?

The findings from Tables 8 to 11 shed light on the proxemics styles used by teachers, students, and administrators at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. The findings suggest that individuals at both universities demonstrate a level of awareness and practice various proxemic styles that contribute to effective communication. These findings have implications for creating a conducive communication environment in educational settings. By recognizing and respecting personal space, utilizing nonverbal cues, and fostering approachability, universities can promote positive and engaging communication between teachers and students.

Studies by Argyle & Dean (1965), Mehrabian (1972), Sommer (1969), Knapp & Hall (2002), Mehrabian (1967), and Argyle & Cook (1976) have supported the findings of this study, highlighting the significance of spatial positioning, personal space, and nonverbal cues in communication interactions.

The findings align with communication theories such as Edward T. Hall's theory of proxemics, which emphasizes the role of spatial positioning and distance in communication. Furthermore, Social Learning Theory highlights the importance of the social environment in shaping proxemic styles and suggests that creating a positive and supportive environment can lead to the adoption of effective proxemic practices.

What are the perceptions and attitudes of undergraduates towards proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?

The findings from Tables 12 to 14 provide insights into the perceptions and attitudes of undergraduates towards proxemics at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University.

The findings suggest that individuals at the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University have positive perceptions and attitudes towards proxemics in communication. They recognize the impact of proxemics, the importance of being aware of it, and the significance of personal space for comfort and well-being.

Previous studies such as those by Hall (1966), Argyle & Henderson (1984), Hall (1963), and Knapp & Hall (1997), support the findings of this study. These studies have emphasized the impact of proxemics on communication and individuals' perceptions of its importance. Communication Accommodation Theory underscores the role of individuals' perceptions and attitudes in shaping their accommodation of proxemics, and these findings suggest a positive inclination towards recognizing and valuing proxemics.

How does proxemics impact undergraduates' engagement, participation, and learning outcomes in classrooms within the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University?

The findings from Tables 16 to 18 shed light on how proxemics impacts student engagement, participation, and learning outcomes in classrooms within the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. The findings suggest that proxemics plays a significant role in student engagement, participation, and

learning outcomes within the classroom setting. Students at the two universities perceive proxemics as an influential factor that impacts their level of engagement, willingness to participate, and academic achievement.

Previous studies by Christensen et al. (2012), Hagenauer et al. (2015), Slavin (2014), Fredricks et al. (2011), Vannini et al. (2012), and Kyndt et al. (2014) support the findings of this study. These studies have demonstrated the positive relationship between proxemics and student engagement, participation, and learning outcomes. The Social Learning Theory also aligns with the findings, as it emphasizes the importance of environmental factors, including proxemics, in influencing individuals' willingness to participate in social interactions (Bandura, 1977).

Conclusion

Proxemics, the study of spatial relationships and communication, plays a significant role in shaping student-lecture interaction within the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University. This research has highlighted the importance of understanding and consciously utilizing proxemics to enhance communication and foster a conducive learning environment, through an examination of proxemic behaviours such as personal space, seating arrangements, and physical gestures.

By recognizing the diverse cultural backgrounds and individual preferences of students, educators can tailor their communication strategies to accommodate different proxemic needs. This includes providing adequate personal space, promoting a sense of inclusivity, and employing non-verbal cues that facilitate understanding and connection. It is crucial for universities to prioritize proxemics as an integral aspect of organisational communication. By doing so, they can cultivate an environment that promotes effective student-lecturer interaction, encourages collaboration, and fosters a sense of belonging among students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Proxemics awareness programs should be incorporated into the

- curriculum to educate students about its importance.
2. Opportunities should be created for appropriate physical proximity to encourage active student participation.
 3. Informal interactions outside the classroom should be encouraged to establish rapport and open communication.
 4. Cultural sensitivity and awareness should be promoted in order to respect and accommodate diverse proxemic norms.

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